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Gamification to engage engineering skills in technical higher education: an experimental approach

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ABSTRACT

The mechatronics industry is fully under development in every area. With the upcoming era of Industry 4.0 things will change in the industry. While the industry is focussing on being ready for the industry 4.0, also the universities are preparing students for this new era. Projects inside the university are very important for creating the attitude and skills that are required, where the V-model (VDI-2206) is used as designing technique. Systems engineering is more than applying the V-model, it's also having the right mind-set and attitude in the various phases during a project. In the first year of the mechatronics department students need to apply systems engineering in the projects, where the age of the students are between 16 and 20 years. In the first years project called, "Smart Industry Mechatronics (SIM)", gamification is used as an experiment to optimize the systems engineering process, where students and teachers are getting familiar with the world of Industry 4.0, and to use and optimize the talents of the students. This paper describes the process and methods that are used for implementing gamification inside the SIM project.

Conference Key Areas: Mechatronics, Systems engineering, Gamification

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INTRODUCTION

Industry 4.0 is currently the trend in automation and data exchange in manufacturing technologies [1]. Industry 4.0 describes cyber-physical systems and combines them with technologies like the internet of things and cloud computing. By applying these techniques it's possible to create a "smart factory". In the Netherlands the industry 4.0 is called "Smart Industry" [2].

For education it's important that students can combine knowledge with technical skills. The University is applying systems engineering as a way of working during projects. Students cooperate in project groups, with different roles and tasks. In 2013 the department of mechatronics did a project with local industrial companies to find out which way of working needs to be implemented in the education. The outcome of the project is that students need to apply a systematic approach that covers all the aspects during a project [15]. From the results of this project, the university has chosen to implement the V-model [3] inside their mechatronics projects.

Students who start at the university of applied sciences have minimal knowledge about the latest techniques and designing methodologies. To engage the motivation of the students, gamification is used in the first years to do research about the technical aspects and to learn and to implement technical knowledge in the project combined with systems engineering.

1 SYSTEMS ENGINEERING

One of the greatest stumbling blocks during any product development is the enthusiasm demonstrated by group members who, after reading the assignment, immediately set to work on construction, only to discover at a later stage that they have forgotten something. The more advanced the stage the project has reached, the more complex and the more expensive it becomes to still make changes. It is therefore extremely important to work systematically during the development process. As improvements are achieved in the way in which the steps are taken, the project will advance more smoothly, and at the end you will reach the finishing point faster. However, the most important point is, that if you work through the steps in the V-Model correctly, you will arrive at a guaranteed good design.

Fig. 1: General overview V-model

The input for this model consists of the requirements of the assignment given to develop, these are the user requirements and system requirements. On the left-hand side of the V is the system design. In other words, here is determined what the system will look like. Here is decided which issues will be solved through mechanical engineering, which through electronic engineering, and how the relationship and communication between these disciplines will be structured. At the bottom of the V-model, the actual development process takes place. The mechanical components take on their real form. The electrical components are selected and designed. The logistics (software, protocols, instructions, etc.) that enable all components within the system to function and communicate are described. However, because this is an industrial standard, it also simultaneously considers the manufacturability, the distribution of the

products around the world, the useful life, the maintenance, etc. A product of which a million units are to be produced must be designed differently from a product of which just ten are to be produced. A product that needs to last 10 years will be designed differently from a product for a single use. One can imagine that with an extremely costly product, suitability for repair is more important than for a relatively cheap product.

On the right-hand side of the V, implementation, testing and checks are carried out. No matter how hard the designers try, every design always contains some errors. This model is therefore produced to provide an answer to the complexity involved in mechatronic systems. Within the university projects, however, far less emphasis will be placed on reproducibility, investments, maintenance, etc.; instead, more focus will be placed on the single production of a functioning model. We have therefore somewhat simplified the V-Model by specifically designating the steps which must be taken.

Fig. 2: Simplified version V-model.

2 GAMIFICATION

Gamification is a relatively new term, but the concept of gamification is not new. Gamification is used for all kinds of different purposes. From training purpose for economics, till education purposes, but gamification is never used in relationship till systems engineering.

The term gamification has many times been defined by various persons. The most commonly accepted of gamification is “Gamification is the use of game mechanics to non-game activities in order to influence people’s behavior” [4].

Game mechanisms are constructs of rules and techniques that are used for implementing gamification. Typical game mechanism that can be used are: points, levels, challenges, trophies, badges or achievements [11].

A second game technique that guides and motivates players are game aesthetics. Game aesthetics are the desirable emotional responses from the player while he interacts with the game. Emotions like fun, trust, surprise and satisfaction are able to drive action and engagement [6].

To integrate gamification in systems engineering it is crucial to understand why and how mechanisms to positively influence people. To understand these mechanisms models of motivation and behavior from the field of psychology needs to be investigated. Wu (2011) analyses Maslow hierarchy of needs [8], b.F. Skinner’s

behavior model and Csikszentmihalyi's Flow theory [9] and concludes that needs and motivators are similar to game dynamics and mechanism [8].

Fig. 3 Maslow/Pink Model – created by Micheal Wu PH, scientis Lithium Technolgy (Wu, 2011)

According to Beza, gamification techniques needs to be done in an well-defined environment [6]. The main question that needs to be answered for applying gamification is: “What kind of behavior do you achieved, and how are you going to implement that” [11].

3 FOGG BEHAVIOR MODEL

For implementing gamification several canvas models can be used as a base platform [14]. However a lot of canvas models can provide a lot of details which can be used for setting up the game. For the SIM project, the fogg behavior model can be used as a starting point for gamification [12]. The fogg behavior model shows that three elements must converge at the same moment for a behavior to occur: motivation, ability and trigger, as can be seen in figure 4. When the Fogg Behavior Model (FBM) is used as a guide, designers can identify what stops people from performing behaviors that designers seeks and it also helps academics to understand behavior change better.

Fig. 4 Fogg's behavior model, created by dr. BJ. FOGG

The FBM highlights three principal elements, motivators, simplicity factors and triggers. These three elements have all specifically subcomponents. According Fogg, triggers might seem simple on the surface, but they can be powerful in their simplicity.

The FBM has three main elements, one of which is Ability. In order to perform a target behavior, a person must have the ability to do so. According Fogg designers of persuasive experiences sometimes assume people have more ability than they really do. There are two paths to increasing ability. You can train people, giving them more skills, more ability to do the target behavior. That's the hard path. The better path is to make the target behavior easier to do. Fogg calls this simplicity [12]. In his behavior

model sometimes the term ability can be swapped with the term simplicity. Ability is the correct general term in the model, but in practice simplicity is what persuasion designers should seek. By focusing on simplicity of the target behavior you increase ability. Simplification of the assignment is necessary to keep the motivation and the right window according Fogg's motivation. The third element of the Fogg Behavior Model are triggers. Without a trigger, the desired behavior will not happen. Triggers can be useful to activate a human behavior. Triggers can be external, like an alarm sounding. Other times, the trigger can come from our daily routine. An effective trigger for a small behavior can lead people to perform harder behaviors. According Fogg, it's a natural chain of events that an effective trigger puts into motion [12].

According Fogg, simplification of the assignment is necessary to keep motivation. Simplification is only needed when the ability doesn't match with the expectations and the chosen triggers. The SIM project is using several types of simplification, so that groups can go through all aspects of the V-model.

Groups are formatted by the project coordinator. The groups exist between 6 and 8 persons. The groups are formatted inside a class, with a maximum of 32 students in class.

4 FIRST YEAR PROJECT MECHATRONIC

The department of mechatronics, of the university of applied science has strong connection with the high-tech industry. Most of the graduated students will be junior employees in those companies. That's why the systematic approach behind a project needs to be developed on the university. The main goal of the first years project of the mechatronics department is that students, needs to cooperate in several project groups and get familiar with process that's behind the development of a mechatronic system. The first years project theme is the "Smart Industry".

The curriculum of department of mechatronics contains four quarters. Every quarter exist of 10 weeks. The duration of the whole SIM project takes 30 weeks, where the projects is divided in three parts; SIM1, SIM2 and SIM3. The total amount of European Credits are given with by every project, and the total workload for every student is 15ECTS divided over these three periods.

To optimise the maximum result out of a project group a competition can be very useful. Competitions as First Lego League (FLL), First Robotic Competition (FRC) and Robocup are examples whereby technical assignments inspire students [10].

For the SIM project 25 teams will compete in game. The game is to create an autonomous driven vehicle which is capable of picking up objects and to place the objects on a scale. All the weight that is collected and placed on the scale will result in points. The groups have a maximum of 5 minutes to collect as much as possible weight.

The use for gamification inside a project is to stimulate a certain behavior. Focussing on the process will result in a better product of the group. In SIM1 the group must realise an autonomous driven vehicle which is capable of following a black line on a white surface.

In SIM2 the group needs to develop a gripper which is able to pick up objects from the floor, place them on the vehicle and eventually place them back on the floor. The technical specifications are given at the beginning of SIM2. In the game more advanced grippers can be rewarded if they are capable of picking up objects from

various heights and distances. In SIM3 group needs to integrate the solutions of SIM1 and SIM2. In SIM3 the assignments of the SIM1 and SIM2 are placed in a different context.

At the start of the project students have mostly no idea how to start a project or what to do. This often results in a slow start of the project, and that generally effects the final result. Gamification techniques can help groups at the start of the project, but it gives tutors also the possibility to give feedback earlier in the process.

5 IMPLEMENTATION SIM PROJECT

For the setup of the SIM project a canvas model is used [13]. To make this project functional and fun, the theme “Smart industry” is chosen. By adapting this theme students will automatically try to make a link with the new industrial era. Groups will work on different assignments in SIM1 and SIM2. In SIM3, the parts of SIM1 and SIM2 will be integrated in a final product. Another requirement was that “systems engineering” was applied in every SIM-project. The implementation of the game mechanism is bounded to the environment of the university of applied science.

The university environment facilitates workshop areas, a shop, meeting rooms and workplace per group. In the mechanical workshops students can work under supervision on machinery or can print 3D components in our print lab. Other mechanical and electronics parts can be ordered through a shop. A group gets a fixed budget per quarter, which can only be spend within the FHENG environment. For general meeting purposes FHENG facilitates several meeting rooms for groups. Having special meeting rooms makes it possible to have a weekly meeting between a group and a tutor. By having all these facilities, the university environment simulates the industrial way of working on a very basic level.

As described, the main goal during the SIM project, is that students learn to work in a team and to develop a systematically approach for developing a mechatronic system. To optimize the workflow, groups needs to get familiar with the university environment. This means that at the begin of the SIM project, the focus of the project is more in exploring the environment and to see what is possible inside the environment, then on the technical product. Once the group knows what is possible inside the environment to group can think about setting up the technical requirements.

The mechanism of the SIM project is based on the V-model. Groups can go through the V-model by doing task in levels. The V-model is divided in ten levels, as can be seen in Figure 5. After every phase of the V-model a new level is introduced. On this way the tutor is able to give earlier feedback.

Fig. 5: Simplified V-model linked to gamification levels

At the start of the SIM project students have a basic knowledge and are unfamiliar with the habits of procedures inside a new school. In that perspective the scope of SIM1 is in the early levels of the project not only focussing on the technical aspect, but also exploring the environment. In SIM1 and SIM2 students get a full description of what to do. In SIM3 groups are familiar of the way of working, and need to merge the solutions from SIM1 and SIM2 in a final solution. If the solution of SIM1 and SIM2 doesn't match the requirements, groups can improve or fix their solution in SIM3. In this way groups can learn from making decisions by analysing the process. Early made decisions can have a huge impact on the final product. Analysing the process can result in new insights on how to approach a problem and how to improve the quality of the process or product.

The triggers are used to go to next level. In the SIM project the triggers are divided in four categories: general tasks, technical work, documentation and evaluation. In every category groups can score points by doing tasks in every category. Per level you groups can earn maximum 20 points. For every average task, one point can be earned. Complex tasks, or larger tasks, can be rewarded with multiple points. To align the triggers with the ability and talents of the students, a mechanism is created. Groups can go to the next level by succeeding a couple of tasks in every category. This means that there are more tasks written than needs to be done. Triggers works best, when a group believes they are in control. Having options means that group can control the situation. By creating multiple categories, the group can control the situation on several elements. By doing different tasks, students can create their own route to reach the next level.

Triggers can help to increase the ability, but in some situations the needed ability is too big. In these kind of situations simplifications can be applied to a certain task. Other possibilities in this model is that the minimum score that's required for every category can be adapted.

To insure that groups can finalize every project, simplification of the main goal of every project is necessary. Simplification for the SIM project where mainly technical simplifications. In SIM1, for the autonomous driving, all basic hardware was provided by the project organisation. The basic hardware consist of, a vehicle, a microcontroller, a H-bridge for controlling the motors of the vehicle and a battery. To make it easier to realize an autonomous vehicle, a black line was taped on a white surface which they could follow.

In SIM2 essential information about grippers and mechanics was provided. This was for increasing the technical spectrum of the students and to stimulate them. In SIM3 no technical simplifications were introduced. Chosen concepts in SIM1 and SIM2 need to be integrated, fine-tuned and tested in SIM3.

During the SIM project a weekly meeting took place with the tutor. The tutor monitors the process of the group and gives feedback about the tasks. In these meetings the students simulate a company meeting and the tutor will be there as an observer. During the meetings the tutor can decide to give feedback or feedforward information to the group.

6 CONCLUSION

A canvas model can be used for setting up a technical project where gamification techniques are integrated in a systematic approach. One of the key elements to successfully wrapping up a project is the project environment. The university has an environment which simulates processes inside a company. These facilities contribute to the behavior of students and how to approach technical projects. To keep students connected with the industry, the theme "Smart Industry" is chosen for the first years mechatronics project. The smart-industry theme was leading for setting up the technical roadmap for the project. The project is divided over three projects. The results of the first two projects will be integrated in the final product. In every project groups need to work with the V-model. The gamification techniques are mainly applied on the systematic approach. The V-model is divided in ten levels. Going to the next level can be achieved by doing tasks. Tutors evaluate the levels. By creating ten levels, ten evaluations moments are created. This leads into earlier feedback from the tutor and groups that know what to do. By applying gamification in the SIM project, we experienced a positive contribution to the development of skills, attitude and knowledge for the first year students.

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